

Supplemental materials

High silica leucogranites result from sedimentary rock melting - an elemental and Nd-Hf-B isotope demonstration

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List of contents

Data sources for Fig. 1A	2
Tables	
Table S1: Trace element compositions of muscovite, biotite and chlorite.	9
Table S2: Trace element compositions of zircon.	24

Data sources for Fig. 1a

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Table S1 Trace element compositions of muscovite, biotite and chlorite

	Li	Be	B	Sc	V	Cr	Mn	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Ga	Ge	Rb	Sr	Y
	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm						
Biotite																
QL09-22-12	98.0	19.3	234	366	101	2.2	1803	4.19	-	13.8	107	122	10.4	1828	9.08	241
QL09-22-13	81.1	15.7	155	187	94.9	4.3	1198	2.27	-	5.28	83	115	4.31	2356	3.14	12.7
QL09-22-16	246	17.6	193	124	80.1	12.7	3969	6.58	-	6.68	181	117	6.73	1715	3.58	10.8
QL09-23-12	60.2	34.5	193	41.2	11.4	-	589	0.80	-	0.81	33	70	5.35	2219	12.7	3.06
QL09-23-14	104	14.4	122	49.8	10.2	-	1006	1.76	-	-	57	108	10.0	1704	7.37	1.79
QL09-26-15	253	5.45	17.2	258	114	10	4087	7.78	-	3.41	181	90	10.4	1462	4.47	71
QL09-29-29	355	2.59	19.4	170	225	98	3112	23.3	25.3	102	270	70	5.96	440	4.54	23
QL09-29-30	439	2.24	12.5	166	238	116	3445	27.4	26.4	115	303	84	7.86	569	4.59	21
QL09-30-21	271	-	-	126	344	81.9	4073	52.4	54.4	1.63	397	64	9.56	1219	2.45	11
Chlorite																
QL09-21-10	385	22.6	324	97	136	31.0	1831	3.61	-	-	196	129	14.5	755	7.66	23.2
QL09-21-14	530	16.9	333	102	95	32.0	1550	4.71	-	0.51	154	126	15.9	656	7.86	25.4
QL09-21-15	422	13.0	354	98.1	95.6	9.0	1276	3.00	7.54	-	154	119	7.75	736	5.51	21.1
QL09-21-17	356	17.1	362	110	469	172	1114	2.51	-	-	124	137	9.04	723	8.66	21.6
QL09-22-3	503	2.69	12	134	72.1	6	8536	13.6	7.70	2.85	385	146	9.88	940	4.46	256
QL09-22-4	474	2.55	9.7	165	100	14	10129	14.9	-	7.44	427	167	11.8	777	5.88	517
QL09-22-6	619	-	9.6	150	67.1	3	12306	18.5	-	1.03	479	149	14.0	452	2.59	91.0
QL09-22-8	762	1.33	5.7	143	68.1	9	13163	19.2	-	3.13	558	144	13.5	255	3.85	106
QL09-22-14	770	3.56	6.8	143	61.0	40	11006	17.2	-	8.50	510	128	11.2	445	4.61	122
QL09-22-15	606	2.85	13.9	114	60.4	11	9274	13.5	9.72	4.53	418	124	9.69	760	3.15	91.0
QL09-25-5	327	1.84	21.6	87.3	75.5	8	8910	9.19	17.9	-	817	138	9.04	419	11.95	38.7

Table S1 Trace element compositions of muscovite, biotite and chlorite

	Li	Be	B	Sc	V	Cr	Mn	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Ga	Ge	Rb	Sr	Y
	ppm															
QL09-25-6	266	3.22	31.8	119	76.4	12	7394	7.01	15.6	-	682	111	9.66	546	8.20	48.1
QL09-25-8	299	3.26	66.0	139	77.0	12	7253	7.68	11.8	0.57	636	98	8.72	507	6.70	19.5
QL09-25-10	311	5.37	18.7	107	63.4	5	8883	9.04	-	-	867	124	-	386	9.08	56.3
QL09-25-11	264	2.16	17.1	95	66.8	6	8361	9.19	-	1.23	775	107	4.35	606	4.81	4.52
QL09-26-11	517	0.85	-	49.2	65.8	6	11514	25.6	-	9.13	595	142	15.13	26	0.42	18.4
QL09-26-12	607	0.55	7.7	254	93.1	21.7	9572	16.0	18.2	1.10	515	136	8.95	55	3.44	125
QL09-26-13	510	1.87	8.2	94	80.9	17.9	10963	20.6	13.4	8.12	560	157	14.9	42	1.99	19.6
QL09-26-18	670	7.53	39.2	182	80.5	15.1	8827	17.6	19.6	7.93	465	138	12.83	126	6.07	58.3
QI09-27-5	713	2.22	12.9	101	108	43.2	6908	24.9	17.9	0.55	471	104	9.89	315	4.25	167
QI09-27-6	784	1.65	7.46	105	117	30.2	7937	26.8	17.7	1.11	510	99.3	8.46	194	4.77	141
QI09-27-7	806	3.08	9.24	82	107	37.4	7762	24.6	11.8	2.13	506	102	9.12	204	5.14	171
QI09-27-8	481	6.16	16.4	205	113	34.0	6109	23.3	13.1	2.45	393	100	16.45	391	6.79	294
QI09-27-9	626	5.04	10.5	118	100	25.8	6984	28.0	18.1	5.68	452	113	8.93	338	5.78	160
QI09-27-17	838	1.37	6.51	114	118	35.4	7230	26.9	20.1	1.04	499	122	12.38	208	3.89	145
QI09-27-18	909	2.74	8.91	94	109	44.3	7694	27.5	18.7	4.13	530	118	9.97	108	5.63	75.6
QI09-27-19	703	0.54	4.96	103	107	9.3	10391	33.0	27.2	4.59	517	120	14.5	158	4.07	107
QL09-28-1	749	-	-	124	87.9	45.6	7796	21.2	-	-	438	111	8.01	999	2.95	43.1
QL09-28-2	771	1.46	10.4	113	110	43.4	8723	26.4	24.6	-	435	115	8.18	726	4.24	74.6
QL09-28-3	929	3.19	4.33	97	70	41.6	8630	28.1	-	-	495	119	8.05	755	3.94	22.6
QL09-28-8	981	6.52	-	120	85	10.3	11852	26.8	39.0	-	615	111	13.2	201	3.88	105
QL09-28-14	864	1.13	5.79	70	142	38.8	11064	28.7	13.9	-	587	126	6.28	51	3.98	65.7
QL09-28-15	775	0.28	3.86	112	144	62.5	8661	22.5	17.1	-	502	119	6.41	195	4.70	216

Table S1 Trace element compositions of muscovite, biotite and chlorite

	Li	Be	B	Sc	V	Cr	Mn	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Ga	Ge	Rb	Sr	Y
	ppm															
QL09-29-2	442	1.68	14.6	94	184	49.2	4240	26.5	37.4	18.2	388	85.5	5.07	352	3.71	54.5
QL09-29-3	648	3.02	7.69	90	218	76.8	5559	31.3	43.6	16.6	505	97.0	6.81	105	3.31	68.9
QL09-29-4	418	2.05	13.1	122	203	67.9	4469	27.7	31.4	38.5	387	84.9	4.70	258	5.02	85.6
QL09-29-5	497	2.01	12.5	90	204	100	5204	34.3	36.1	64.4	473	91.0	5.69	234	2.94	111
QL09-29-6	471	5.49	13.9	139	237	92.8	4720	33.6	38.2	140	445	80.3	11.54	153	6.65	109
QL09-29-13	555	4.18	18.0	144	214	97.3	3691	22.3	-	190	318	76.5	-	359	7.77	61.9
QL09-29-15	529	3.28	12.0	141	244	42.4	5409	8.25	28.1	60.6	445	97.6	5.22	124	5.72	107
QL09-29-19	633	2.70	9.89	103	285	57.9	5497	27.2	16.8	39.2	442	98.8	10.12	171	5.88	42.9
QL09-29-26	591	4.89	13.1	149	256	73	5673	23.0	31.9	86.0	526	92.9	11.81	61	5.50	306
QL09-29-31	309	1.30	14.1	142	229	82	3081	23.1	32.8	91.9	258	64.9	3.12	443	3.34	20.3
QL09-29-34	332	1.87	16.9	100	210	61	3768	25.7	25.4	50.5	319	79.0	4.81	426	3.14	8.73
QL09-30-5	392	1.33	7.65	62.4	225	66	5947	68.0	64.7	1.78	551	86.3	5.24	123	3.75	12.6
QL09-30-7	355	1.38	7.10	69.8	281	89	4563	58.1	56.4	3.15	460	74.4	5.60	393	5.87	24.5
QL09-30-12	286	0.61	4.83	66.6	263	65	4076	52.9	53.8	3.62	420	67.5	6.66	667	1.90	3.24
QL09-30-17	365	0.74	4.59	38.9	211	91	8502	70.8	74.3	4.34	630	94.2	6.36	2	1.32	35.1
QL09-30-20	371	1.92	11.8	139	402	99	5722	62.1	61.2	3.47	528	84.1	5.86	9	8.48	71.5
QL09-30-22	312	1.66	11.3	163	380	78	5169	57.3	61.5	1.78	464	76.4	6.73	85	8.92	116
QL09-30-29	345	1.12	10.2	174	374	99	4668	56.4	63.0	4.35	454	72.7	5.75	220	10.8	63.1
Muscovite																
QL09-20-1	243	3.66	54.8	143	4.38	-	1088	-	-	-	47.1	138	9.38	2283	0.42	0.23
QL09-20-2	402	3.40	43.4	201	4.17	-	1131	0.57	15.3	-	45.3	146	8.15	2258	0.17	0.24
QL09-20-3	89.3	4.80	32.2	77.0	3.98	-	776	0.83	12.6	-	33.4	121	8.57	2000	0.35	0.21

Table S1 Trace element compositions of muscovite, biotite and chlorite

	Li	Be	B	Sc	V	Cr	Mn	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Ga	Ge	Rb	Sr	Y
	ppm															
QL09-20-4	80.8	4.30	24.8	64.8	6.22	-	597	0.52	13.5	-	26.0	172	9.68	2003	0.46	-
QL09-20-5	455	-	29.9	482	4.61	-	940	0.97	-	-	43.5	169	8.09	2297	0.24	0.47
QL09-20-9	82.8	5.45	33.4	410	13.8	-	859	0.90	-	-	34.9	162	6.66	2277	-	-
QL09-20-19	114	5.68	41.6	184	2.78	-	998	0.82	-	-	44.7	138	7.42	2308	0.17	0.39
QL09-21-1	83.0	3.85	28.1	93.2	7.24	-	871	0.53	-	-	29.6	105	3.83	1488	0.48	0.03
QL09-21-4	64.2	5.28	56.1	52.7	4.39	-	975	1.07	-	-	32.8	70	8.31	1823	0.31	0.09
QL09-21-5	26.3	5.43	52.3	230	9.13	-	794	0.69	-	-	30.9	134	8.81	1682	0.46	0.23
QL09-21-7	333	0.37	35.7	136	1.55	-	1059	0.98	-	-	39.8	121	7.29	1831	0.22	0.35
QL09-21-8	109	1.48	41.8	168	3.34	-	848	0.64	-	-	35.4	135	8.52	1731	0.38	0.22
QL09-21-9	68.0	3.58	55.0	170	10.8	1.05	800	0.62	-	-	33.5	102	8.57	1729	0.43	0.18
QL09-22-1	316	2.59	22.0	20.4	-	-	1006	0.36	-	-	17.7	76.0	3.41	1094	0.68	-
QL09-22-7	186	9.90	42.9	575	117	30.6	912	2.48	-	1.24	21.5	174	6.10	1304	1.94	8.93
QL09-22-10	136	3.16	26.9	292	26.1	-	1039	2.02	-	1.50	45.3	110	3.86	1116	0.87	3.72
QL09-23-7	48.9	9.35	219	97.4	84.9	26.2	192	0.54	-	0.64	27.9	136	4.28	1173	3.58	2.04
QL09-23-10	31.4	12.4	146	45.9	10.5	0.73	888	0.97	-	0.65	35.5	103	4.88	1241	2.66	3.15
QL09-23-11	71.7	14.5	80.3	24.1	3.0	-	1480	0.56	-	0.45	22.8	83.9	3.73	543	2.02	0.28
QL09-23-14	104	14.4	122	49.8	10.2	-	1006	1.76	-	-	56.9	108	10.0	1704	7.37	1.79
QL09-23-15	32.7	11.0	61.6	23.4	2.72	-	693	0.48	-	0.56	25.8	84.2	3.70	1052	2.15	0.29
QL09-23-16	34.3	11.0	81.3	23.8	2.50	-	762	0.86	-	-	35.2	84.2	4.10	1374	2.12	0.56
QL09-23-17	123	3.12	25.7	53.5	4.90	-	635	0.51	-	-	20.7	92.9	4.41	1140	0.88	0.07
QL09-23-18	34.5	6.90	97.9	26.0	3.88	-	1002	1.16	-	-	46.0	80.0	4.20	1204	2.30	2.68
QL09-23-19	30.4	11.5	109	26.9	5.28	1.18	1910	2.31	-	2.38	84.8	83.5	3.96	1115	5.13	11.7

Table S1 Trace element compositions of muscovite, biotite and chlorite

	Li	Be	B	Sc	V	Cr	Mn	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Ga	Ge	Rb	Sr	Y
	ppm															
QL09-24-1	148	11.1	55.9	108	10.2	-	1248	1.10	-	-	44.6	92.7	3.22	1519	0.29	0.02
QL09-24-4	40.1	3.5	67.4	243	16.7	-	908	0.62	-	-	34.1	121	5.41	1401	1.29	0.10
QL09-24-5	66.9	4.24	55.4	236	18.1	-	991	0.87	-	-	36.6	119	4.15	1353	0.40	0.16
QL09-24-6	28.5	2.69	60.5	244	16.0	-	872	0.90	-	-	31.1	119	4.23	1442	0.70	0.15
QL09-24-7	98.6	2.48	35.2	401	12.0	-	908	1.02	-	-	33.3	130	5.03	1474	0.53	0.21
QL09-24-8	56.3	3.80	35.0	321	7.04	-	843	0.92	-	-	31.8	124	5.74	1410	0.69	0.18
QL09-24-9	95.5	2.09	30.7	393	12.7	-	935	0.92	-	-	35.6	130	5.92	1483	0.47	0.22
QL09-24-10	80.5	2.91	30.3	356	16.7	-	1001	1.02	-	-	36.2	131	4.90	1460	0.51	0.21
QL09-24-11	88.9	2.34	60.5	124	12.3	-	974	0.94	-	-	37.2	94.9	3.90	1360	0.54	0.05
QL09-25-1	35.4	7.65	32.2	160	31.3	-	368	0.73	-	-	18.6	96.7	2.13	935	0.98	0.06
QL09-25-4	38.8	4.27	30.7	105	18.0	-	339	0.65	-	-	15.8	86.3	1.83	933	0.72	-
QL09-25-7	126	5.78	31.8	516	69.8	-	545	1.38	-	-	36.7	131	2.67	1113	0.58	-
QL09-26-5	264	3.04	33.8	143	24.5	2.59	381	0.83	-	-	20.8	82.0	3.95	1000	1.00	-
QL09-26-6	55.0	2.96	25.4	134	19.8	-	345	0.58	-	-	16.8	81.5	3.87	901	0.99	2.31
QL09-26-7	45.8	3.34	28.0	110	16.9	-	345	0.55	-	-	18.8	74.3	2.29	959	0.97	0.25
QL09-27-10	97.8	6.35	33.0	208	79.8	-	319	1.31	-	-	17.6	88.7	2.59	979	0.58	-
QL09-27-11	71.0	4.67	35.1	231	74.0	-	303	1.18	-	-	17.6	92.3	1.76	857	0.58	-
QL09-28-6	238	5.43	57.2	79	10.7	-	616	1.66	-	-	24.7	74.3	-	861	3.38	61.9
QL09-29-23	151	5.89	93.9	24	51.2	-	518	2.19	-	5.78	43.9	39.9	-	1010	90.1	2.14
QL09-30-25	48.9	0.75	151	22	53.5	-	339	2.81	10.1	-	31.8	50.8	-	1549	5.51	0.64

Table S1 Trace element compositions of muscovite, biotite and chlorite

	Mo	Sb	Cs	Ba	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Eu	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er
	ppm														
Biotite															
QL09-22-12	0.52	0.84	68.9	67.9	6.38	15.9	2.50	14.8	6.36	0.08	14.2	3.57	34.7	8.73	28.8
QL09-22-13	0.07	0.32	43.8	56.5	1.9	0.88	0.16	0.65	0.39	0.01	0.67	0.18	1.99	0.47	1.72
QL09-22-16	-	0.28	56.0	51.9	1.0	1.23	0.15	0.81	0.14	-	0.49	0.17	1.34	0.36	1.46
QL09-23-12	-	4.22	77.0	39.3	0.2	0.53	0.09	0.29	0.17	-	0.14	0.08	0.37	0.09	0.34
QL09-23-14	-	2.06	73.7	47.0	0.4	0.97	0.16	0.60	0.15	-	0.25	0.08	0.20	0.07	0.28
QL09-26-15	0.23	0.21	38.2	63.0	3.4	12	1.55	8.68	3.83	0.39	6.11	1.56	12.6	2.96	8.91
QL09-29-29	0.42	-	26.6	554	5.2	11	0.44	2.53	0.95	0.12	1.43	0.46	3.53	0.79	2.86
QL09-29-30	0.40	-	33.2	1242	6.6	14	0.69	1.66	1.08	0.11	1.73	0.37	2.52	0.75	2.31
QL09-30-21	0.23	-	172.2	168.1	0.9	2	0.32	1.70	0.40	0.07	1.43	0.22	1.59	0.42	1.36
Chlorite															
QL09-21-10	4.78	7.04	47.8	49.4	3.94	4.78	1.50	6.60	2.74	-	3.22	0.74	4.65	0.87	2.71
QL09-21-14	2.87	7.21	40.8	54.3	5.38	9.37	1.82	8.66	3.31	0.03	4.06	0.81	4.88	1.08	3.27
QL09-21-15	1.69	4.15	34.7	35.8	2.85	5.75	1.25	5.37	3.18	0.02	2.64	0.85	5.63	0.92	3.00
QL09-21-17	2.08	12.2	46.3	51.1	8.17	20.9	3.5	10.3	3.96	0.11	4.31	0.59	5.60	0.89	3.08
QL09-22-3	0.55	0.21	49.7	39.9	1.49	7.53	0.54	3.03	3.08	0.03	10.8	4.06	39.1	9.93	37.0
QL09-22-4	0.44	0.92	23.2	70.2	7.32	46.2	3.3	13.6	11.8	0.15	35.2	12.4	115	25.6	95.1
QL09-22-6	0.23	-	24.1	24.4	2.77	2.47	0.13	1.50	3.12	0.04	4.77	1.38	13.3	3.61	11.2
QL09-22-8	0.97	0.18	20.3	20.8	0.92	3.31	0.30	1.03	0.68	-	1.80	0.81	11.9	3.93	16.3
QL09-22-14	1.33	0.33	30.6	25.0	1.42	3.77	0.52	2.55	0.79	0.02	3.63	1.41	20.7	5.01	22.5
QL09-22-15	0.75	0.20	31.8	30.3	1.40	5.03	0.5	2.5	0.75	0.02	1.37	0.60	10.7	3.25	13.4
QL09-25-5	0.23	1.15	22.6	38.7	6.18	9.66	0.84	4.30	2.35	0.13	6.76	1.40	16.3	4.36	8.03

Table S1 Trace element compositions of muscovite, biotite and chlorite

	Mo	Sb	Cs	Ba	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Eu	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er
	ppm														
QL09-25-6	0.22	2.06	24.2	37.9	3.43	8.10	1.16	4.31	3.50	0.08	8.20	2.56	18.9	3.43	10.6
QL09-25-8	0.49	2.17	27.2	49.2	1.80	4.50	0.59	2.90	2.01	0.04	3.10	1.08	7.27	1.57	4.97
QL09-25-10	-	1.31	24.6	51.9	2.53	5.73	1.45	7.72	9.39	0.29	29.8	4.36	36.2	5.91	17.6
QL09-25-11	0.16	1.23	25.5	35.2	0.4	1.53	0.25	0.79	0.51	-	0.63	0.19	0.89	0.18	0.57
QL09-26-11	-	-	8.9	3.4	0.91	10.0	0.46	6.58	2.45	-	6.01	0.59	5.59	1.35	4.81
QL09-26-12	-	-	12.7	17.7	1.04	3.03	0.83	7.98	4.75	0.05	9.19	2.21	15.3	3.52	11.9
QL09-26-13	0.25	-	8.9	11.4	0.53	2.54	0.27	1.72	0.89	0.02	1.41	0.45	3.33	0.70	2.68
QL09-26-18	0.86	-	30.3	20.0	3.53	15.67	1.99	8.94	4.06	0.28	7.23	1.55	10.71	2.63	7.94
QI09-27-5	23.3	0.48	19.8	72.6	1.85	7.7	1.4	7.24	4.32	0.04	5.78	2.07	19.84	6.31	25.5
QI09-27-6	0.58	-	13.2	64.8	2.52	10.3	2.0	12.15	8.48	0.09	11.2	2.39	19.26	4.48	16.1
QI09-27-7	0.71	0.40	12.3	51.8	1.88	8.91	1.77	7.86	6.13	0.21	9.3	2.17	21.96	5.60	22.5
QI09-27-8	-	0.53	12.8	54.0	4.61	16.1	4.1	27.9	26.9	0.3	35.5	7.53	51.7	11.3	34.9
QI09-27-9	0.37	0.37	16.8	59.2	2.92	8.18	2.20	13.71	10.49	0.18	14.9	3.52	28.2	5.93	20.0
QI09-27-17	0.19	-	8.5	37.0	1.18	4.60	1.08	6.31	4.96	0.06	6.85	1.82	19.72	5.30	17.2
QI09-27-18	0.64	0.53	6.54	45.1	1.58	4.65	1.30	6.79	5.05	0.18	6.79	1.66	13.20	3.01	10.7
QI09-27-19	0.30	-	9.74	31.2	1.13	2.80	0.54	2.70	3.34	0.11	4.53	1.14	13.48	3.46	12.9
QL09-28-1	1.01	-	60.5	46.1	0.94	3.79	0.75	4.26	0.87	0.09	1.06	0.35	4.32	1.26	5.71
QL09-28-2	0.67	-	41.6	47.9	1.80	10.2	1.79	7.47	1.91	0.04	3.61	0.95	11.1	2.76	9.88
QL09-28-3	0.73	-	43.3	59.7	0.66	2.63	0.49	1.30	0.42	-	1.33	0.29	3.11	0.85	2.79
QL09-28-8	-	-	17.3	35.6	2.27	4.04	0.90	8.21	4.22	0.13	7.70	1.32	12.0	2.77	14.0
QL09-28-14	0.58	-	6.6	30.5	0.65	2.19	0.52	2.26	2.51	0.07	3.76	1.07	9.54	2.36	8.94
QL09-28-15	2.03	-	22.3	83.0	0.89	6.77	1.46	7.97	4.20	0.04	5.37	1.59	18.7	6.50	27.2

Table S1 Trace element compositions of muscovite, biotite and chlorite

	Mo	Sb	Cs	Ba	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Eu	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er
	ppm														
QL09-29-2	0.12	-	22.1	117	0.98	4.00	0.78	3.31	1.28	0.10	1.80	0.57	6.70	1.68	6.25
QL09-29-3	0.29	-	21.5	29.6	0.74	2.56	0.63	4.07	1.70	0.22	3.93	0.97	9.09	2.47	8.59
QL09-29-4	0.08	-	19.9	85.3	1.53	5.53	1.03	5.44	2.70	0.41	4.97	1.08	11.1	2.80	10.38
QL09-29-5	-	-	12.4	138	1.77	5.55	1.03	4.44	2.05	-	5.54	1.27	11.75	3.05	12.63
QL09-29-6	0.3	0.31	17.2	97.5	2.73	8.48	1.73	9.64	4.84	0.46	6.99	1.43	12.34	3.40	12.33
QL09-29-13	1.0	-	19.0	111	3.07	17.8	3.75	13.14	8.83	0.16	9.48	1.79	12.50	2.42	8.28
QL09-29-15	-	-	7.0	43.7	0.90	3.15	0.70	4.19	2.69	0.03	5.36	1.15	11.65	3.18	10.7
QL09-29-19	-	0.28	30.9	29.9	2.04	8.69	1.82	8.51	2.87	1.60	4.49	0.85	8.80	1.62	5.29
QL09-29-26	0.21	0.31	12.8	47.3	2.81	9.51	1.96	13.77	11.91	0.60	21.23	6.45	50.24	12.76	39.03
QL09-29-31	0.19	-	24.7	519	2.77	4.69	0.45	2.91	1.12	0.04	0.72	0.39	3.20	0.70	2.47
QL09-29-34	0.23	-	22.4	130	0.40	1.42	0.19	0.96	0.38	-	0.76	0.16	1.09	0.29	0.99
QL09-30-5	-	-	21.0	45.6	0.70	1.41	0.34	1.71	0.76	0.11	1.11	0.27	2.63	0.43	1.36
QL09-30-7	-	-	49.7	103	1.05	2.92	0.60	2.62	0.96	0.22	1.70	0.53	3.84	0.97	2.91
QL09-30-12	-	-	21.5	377	0.27	0.36	0.08	0.34	0.17	0.03	0.25	0.02	0.51	0.08	0.19
QL09-30-17	-	-	1.81	11.9	0.27	0.56	0.08	0.37	0.39	0.04	1.24	0.50	5.41	1.41	4.71
QL09-30-20	0.10	-	5.28	30.5	1.40	2.83	0.78	3.27	2.30	0.53	3.97	1.09	9.10	2.36	7.39
QL09-30-22	-	0.32	6.32	31.1	1.13	2.07	0.53	2.44	1.31	0.14	3.65	1.35	12.62	3.32	11.0
QL09-30-29	0.18	0.12	22.5	352	1.97	3.57	0.94	4.29	1.76	0.13	3.70	1.06	9.06	2.35	7.60
Muscovite															
QL09-20-1	0.82	-	58.7	11.3	-	0.15	-	-	-	0.08	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-20-2	1.30	-	49.7	11.1	-	-	-	-	-	0.31	-	-	-	-	-

Table S1 Trace element compositions of muscovite, biotite and chlorite

	Mo	Sb	Cs	Ba	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Eu	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er
	ppm														
QL09-20-3	0.96	-	69.8	15.2	-	-	-	0.08	-	0.04	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-20-4	0.69	-	33.9	30.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-20-5	0.87	-	33.1	9.42	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-20-9	1.36	-	39.5	15.7	-	0.46	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-20-19	1.35	-	54.3	9.86	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-21-1	0.16	-	37.2	36.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-21-4	1.44	-	73.3	18.7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-21-5	0.93	-	50.9	17.7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-21-7	1.56	-	45.6	14.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.01
QL09-21-8	1.19	-	39.3	16.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-21-9	1.29	-	69.9	25.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-22-1	-	-	25.3	20.3	0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-22-7	-	-	45.3	46.4	4.00	14.27	0.95	4.18	1.65	-	2.54	0.38	1.75	0.37	1.04
QL09-22-10	0.26	-	26.9	99.8	1.76	1.10	0.44	1.75	0.48	0.02	0.63	0.10	0.81	0.14	0.51
QL09-23-7	-	1.15	113	45.9	0.35	0.82	0.15	0.67	0.32	-	0.59	0.11	0.59	0.13	0.50
QL09-23-10	0.29	0.18	33.4	41.2	0.79	1.21	0.41	1.42	0.57	0.02	0.70	0.10	0.61	0.13	0.21
QL09-23-11	-	0.22	25.2	7.4	0.11	0.22	0.05	0.07	-	-	0.05	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.03
QL09-23-14	-	2.06	73.7	47.0	0.40	0.97	0.16	0.60	0.15	-	0.25	0.08	0.20	0.07	0.28
QL09-23-15	-	0.19	49.1	57.6	0.07	0.08	0.04	0.02	0.03	-	0.07	0.04	0.02	0.03	0.04
QL09-23-16	-	0.24	35.4	41.3	0.18	0.16	0.06	0.11	0.10	-	0.10	0.07	0.12	0.04	0.08
QL09-23-17	0.12	-	25.8	40.1	0.05	0.02	-	0.03	0.04	-	0.08	0.05	0.03	0.04	0.05
QL09-23-18	0.95	-	43.8	37.4	0.84	0.88	0.40	1.25	0.46	0.02	0.29	0.12	0.66	0.14	0.26

Table S1 Trace element compositions of muscovite, biotite and chlorite

	Mo	Sb	Cs	Ba	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Eu	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er
	ppm														
QL09-23-19	1.79	0.23	34.1	60.8	3.29	5.08	1.45	5.27	2.45	0.09	2.14	0.40	2.45	0.51	1.49
QL09-24-1	-	-	65.8	16.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.02
QL09-24-4	0.96	-	66.8	9.08	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.01
QL09-24-5	0.88	-	57.7	8.22	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.01
QL09-24-6	1.28	-	91.8	5.57	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.01
QL09-24-7	1.08	-	66.9	8.51	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.06
QL09-24-8	1.20	-	57.8	7.23	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.01
QL09-24-9	1.14	-	66.6	5.93	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.01
QL09-24-10	0.71	-	64.1	6.34	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.05
QL09-24-11	1.06	-	61.3	6.98	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-25-1	-	-	19.1	62.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-25-4	-	-	18.8	43.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-25-7	-	-	19.3	86.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-26-5	-	-	18.2	170	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-26-6	-	-	18.2	63.9	0.06	0.13	0.02	0.11	-	0.03	0.14	0.02	0.31	0.05	0.23
QL09-26-7	-	-	20.1	117	0.07	0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-27-10	-	-	20.5	135	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-27-11	-	-	16.6	73.9	0.04	0.41	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
QL09-28-6	-	-	14.9	132	0.95	63.3	0.20	1.39	0.95	0.10	3.98	1.07	7.78	1.75	7.45
QL09-29-23	-	-	24.5	131	2.10	2.47	0.24	0.98	0.15	0.25	-	0.04	0.29	0.05	0.23
QL09-30-25	-	-	29.6	205	0.17	0.14	0.02	0.14	-	0.04	0.05	-	-	0.01	0.09

Table S1 Trace element compositions of muscovite, biotite and chlorite

	Tm	Yb	Lu	W	Tl	Pb	Bi	Th	U	Zr	Hf	Nb	Ta	Nb/Ta	Zr/Hf
	ppm														
Biotite															
QL09-22-12	4.52	32.6	4.61	25.6	6.5	144	1.86	108	40.7	55.8	4.74	959	117	8	12
QL09-22-13	0.39	3.97	0.67	0.4	8.11	49.7	0.42	30.1	0.3	29.0	3.22	12.7	0.70	18	9
QL09-22-16	0.25	3.05	0.54	0.24	6.40	72.1	0.19	11.5	0.33	16.4	1.69	20.2	1.46	14	10
QL09-23-12	0.10	0.73	0.20	1.00	11.3	5.02	-	0.9	0.59	4.92	0.43	3.30	0.68	5	11
QL09-23-14	0.08	0.60	0.16	14.1	7.55	9.58	-	0.5	0.46	3.31	0.33	2.28	0.56	4	10
QL09-26-15	1.71	12.0	1.56	22.5	4.17	94.1	0.09	8.0	8.57	2.57	0.39	463	56.4	8	7
QL09-29-29	0.50	3.75	0.56	2.66	2.14	63.6	-	0.7	0.53	1.32	0.26	209	12.1	17	5
QL09-29-30	0.44	2.84	0.37	1.57	3.56	74.3	-	1.67	0.44	1.33	0.14	149	10.5	14	10
QL09-30-21	0.18	1.43	0.16	2.21	6.22	15.4	-	0.20	0.51	0.29	-	137	27.8	5	
Chlorite															
QL09-21-10	0.41	3.62	0.46	33.8	3.31	39.2	-	8.92	125	2.37	0.18	337	18.9	18	13
QL09-21-14	0.49	3.82	0.57	51.4	2.85	38.2	0.26	28.5	111	52.56	2.29	401	17.8	23	23
QL09-21-15	0.47	3.53	0.50	14.5	2.96	30.0	-	58.7	97.0	12.3	1.00	337	29.3	12	12
QL09-21-17	0.58	3.68	0.66	68.4	3.11	41.4	0.08	21.5	73.7	11.8	0.89	448	17.2	26	13
QL09-22-3	5.51	40.6	6.00	6.28	4.64	101	-	1.5	4.69	0.64	0.08	219	22.0	10	8
QL09-22-4	15.8	95.4	14.2	14.5	3.26	262	0.11	115	66.2	20.6	0.78	504	42.3	12	26
QL09-22-6	1.77	12.0	2.10	2.18	1.94	99.3	-	0.27	2.56	0.34	0.11	110	8.47	13	3
QL09-22-8	2.72	21.1	2.98	4.17	1.23	156	-	2.97	7.52	1.24	0.18	245	23.3	11	7
QL09-22-14	3.22	21.8	3.67	7.12	2.04	129	-	13.63	7.69	6.06	0.70	383	22.1	17	9
QL09-22-15	2.24	17.5	2.36	3.07	3.19	91.4	0.14	4.07	2.28	2.02	0.25	192	13.8	14	8
QL09-25-5	1.51	8.48	1.25	35.2	2.64	407	-	4.43	15.90	0.40	0.10	265	29.7	9	4

Table S1 Trace element compositions of muscovite, biotite and chlorite

	Tm	Yb	Lu	W	Tl	Pb	Bi	Th	U	Zr	Hf	Nb	Ta	Nb/Ta	Zr/Hf
	ppm														
QL09-25-6	1.54	10.73	1.19	58.4	2.63	317	-	2.61	21.23	0.97	0.46	602	38.2	16	2
QL09-25-8	0.72	4.63	0.59	60.8	2.65	342	-	9.32	12.48	2.41	0.25	200	11.6	17	10
QL09-25-10	3.40	15.0	2.31	53.2	1.67	647	-	37.5	80.0	1.47	0.24	328	35.8	9	6
QL09-25-11	0.07	0.75	0.10	1.97	2.75	248	-	3.45	0.67	1.48	0.17	72.4	7.61	10	9
QL09-26-11	0.33	26.0	0.50	1.25	-	150	0.70	14.2	9.62	0.32	-	39.9	2.55	16	
QL09-26-12	1.73	10.4	1.32	3.20	0.36	97.9	-	0.06	1.20	0.93	0.43	582	47.6	12	2
QL09-26-13	0.48	2.79	0.35	1.37	0.26	172	-	0.36	1.29	0.21	0.04	116	8.95	13	5
QL09-26-18	1.18	8.31	1.22	10.3	0.77	185	-	1.72	7.89	1.36	0.43	421	28.1	15	3
Ql09-27-5	4.52	30.5	4.17	5.79	1.23	288	0.18	0.25	4.57	0.96	0.25	182	8.06	23	4
Ql09-27-6	2.85	20.1	2.43	2.81	0.72	311	-	0.06	1.14	0.81	0.16	181	12.8	14	5
Ql09-27-7	3.90	28.9	3.41	3.57	0.68	370	-	0.31	3.04	1.02	0.14	167	13.8	12	7
Ql09-27-8	6.64	50.0	6.47	8.30	1.88	335	-	0.26	6.18	1.41	0.34	403	46.7	9	4
Ql09-27-9	3.28	24.3	3.29	3.71	1.24	380	-	1.29	2.25	1.06	0.24	156	15.7	10	4
Ql09-27-17	2.88	23.0	2.76	3.26	0.75	196	-	0.02	1.97	1.04	0.17	188	17.1	11	6
Ql09-27-18	1.61	11.2	1.31	3.11	0.46	398	-	0.46	4.57	1.07	0.24	190	15.7	12	4
Ql09-27-19	2.09	16.8	2.24	5.40	0.44	162	0.19	27.2	2.24	5.28	0.53	174	42.3	4	10
QL09-28-1	1.06	6.95	0.91	3.36	5.59	8.45	-	0.24	0.50	0.79	0.11	172	8.16	21	7
QL09-28-2	1.90	12.4	1.80	1.99	4.05	6.35	-	0.38	1.50	0.45	0.14	168	10.2	16	3
QL09-28-3	0.56	3.10	0.53	2.88	4.40	94.9	-	1.07	1.26	0.87	0.23	120	11.4	11	4
QL09-28-8	2.19	14.8	2.17	3.87	1.34	233	-	5.48	5.11	3.03	0.47	248	18.2	14	6
QL09-28-14	1.64	11.3	1.26	1.00	0.26	133	-	2.67	2.51	0.48	-	86.6	4.93	18	
QL09-28-15	4.56	33.4	3.94	2.72	1.42	2.60	-	1.50	1.51	1.15	0.24	271	9.72	28	5

Table S1 Trace element compositions of muscovite, biotite and chlorite

	Tm	Yb	Lu	W	Tl	Pb	Bi	Th	U	Zr	Hf	Nb	Ta	Nb/Ta	Zr/Hf
	ppm														
QL09-29-2	0.95	7.74	0.87	1.60	1.30	45.4	-	0.01	0.86	0.33	0.11	141	14.4	10	3
QL09-29-3	1.39	9.77	1.19	1.95	0.54	62.3	-	0.36	2.65	0.71	0.07	163	11.9	14	10
QL09-29-4	1.66	10.8	1.38	2.17	1.11	67.1	-	0.11	3.15	1.33	0.14	167	11.0	15	9
QL09-29-5	2.04	13.7	1.63	1.05	0.99	86.5	-	0.19	0.79	0.43	-	130	11.2	12	
QL09-29-6	2.01	16.0	2.06	3.88	0.73	111	-	13.25	3.14	5.88	0.45	180	9.47	19	13
QL09-29-13	0.92	7.21	0.63	1.49	1.06	147	-	40.84	3.51	8.77	0.41	268	21.7	12	21
QL09-29-15	1.61	11.4	1.52	2.41	0.53	103	-	0.01	1.43	1.02	0.09	232	28.2	8	11
QL09-29-19	0.66	5.96	0.67	3.37	0.98	50.1	-	3.39	2.80	1.38	-	215	25.5	8	
QL09-29-26	6.42	39.7	5.14	3.64	0.50	160	-	2.92	10.51	0.96	0.05	242	18.5	13	21
QL09-29-31	0.39	2.47	0.45	1.62	2.45	48.7	-	0.89	0.69	1.32	0.22	135	9.71	14	6
QL09-29-34	0.14	1.14	0.15	1.28	1.60	53.9	-	2.03	0.25	1.21	0.06	102	6.18	16	20
QL09-30-5	0.18	1.15	0.15	1.34	0.81	158	-	0.01	0.54	0.12	0.01	59.9	8.49	7	10
QL09-30-7	0.49	2.74	0.32	2.66	2.12	74.8	-	0.91	1.40	0.56	0.09	98.4	15.7	6	7
QL09-30-12	0.05	0.22	0.04	1.44	3.56	59.2	-	-	0.09	0.22	0.04	89.4	14.6	6	6
QL09-30-17	0.78	4.82	0.56	0.45	-	54.7	-	0.46	0.16	0.15	-	21.3	2.97	7	
QL09-30-20	1.18	7.88	0.92	3.24	-	164	-	0.12	2.22	1.09	0.28	195	17.7	11	4
QL09-30-22	1.89	11.3	1.31	3.63	0.39	90.0	-	0.13	0.89	0.74	0.18	241	80.1	3	4
QL09-30-29	1.20	9.32	1.10	3.60	1.43	45.7	-	0.94	1.56	0.78	0.08	226	27.3	8	10
Muscovite															
QL09-20-1	-	-	-	103	6.47	3.16	-	0.15	-	1.49	0.67	154	31.5	4.89	2.24
QL09-20-2	-	0.31	0.25	97.8	6.16	3.44	-	-	-	1.37	0.79	171	29.8	5.73	1.72

Table S1 Trace element compositions of muscovite, biotite and chlorite

	Tm	Yb	Lu	W	Tl	Pb	Bi	Th	U	Zr	Hf	Nb	Ta	Nb/Ta	Zr/Hf
	ppm														
QL09-20-3	-	-	-	88.2	5.08	3.95	-	-	0.05	1.38	0.41	166	52.2	3.18	3.37
QL09-20-4	-	-	-	51.8	4.77	5.69	-	-	-	1.16	0.65	134	77.3	1.73	1.79
QL09-20-5	-	0.35	-	98.2	5.83	3.04	-	-	-	1.93	0.82	229	29.5	7.78	2.35
QL09-20-9	-	0.37	-	119	5.97	2.98	-	0.16	-	1.86	0.91	239	34.0	7.04	2.06
QL09-20-19	-	-	0.03	107	6.31	2.95	-	-	-	1.50	0.89	171	35.5	4.82	1.68
QL09-21-1	-	-	-	51.8	3.89	4.41	-	-	-	0.73	0.13	32.8	8.0	4.08	5.46
QL09-21-4	-	0.42	0.03	97.9	4.85	3.48	-	-	-	2.20	1.07	104	39.9	2.61	2.06
QL09-21-5	-	0.65	0.13	115	4.25	4.42	-	0.22	-	1.83	0.88	159	44.8	3.56	2.09
QL09-21-7	-	0.81	0.24	134	4.53	3.07	-	-	-	1.95	0.98	172	37.3	4.60	2.00
QL09-21-8	-	0.52	0.16	104	4.56	4.46	-	-	-	1.76	0.83	171	32.5	5.25	2.12
QL09-21-9	-	0.45	0.09	132	4.38	3.84	-	-	-	1.70	0.82	80	36.0	2.22	2.07
QL09-22-1	-	-	-	2.20	3.05	4.38	-	-	-	0.15	-	0	-		
QL09-22-7	0.09	0.93	0.13	21.7	3.24	155	-	17.7	0.08	4.36	0.30	149	9.46	15.8	14.4
QL09-22-10	0.10	0.68	0.08	12.4	3.00	55.8	0.14	11.8	0.83	3.31	0.34	55.3	4.54	12.2	9.8
QL09-23-7	0.09	0.91	0.20	7.62	5.22	4.55	-	2.96	1.82	8.06	0.54	100	7.42	13.4	14.8
QL09-23-10	0.06	0.41	0.09	1.21	4.23	14.8	-	5.63	7.09	9.45	0.55	3.31	0.35	9.37	17.2
QL09-23-11	0.03	0.14	0.04	0.08	2.34	5.31	0.05	0.20	0.15	1.26	0.14	0.57	0.09	6.39	9.1
QL09-23-14	0.08	0.60	0.16	14.1	7.55	9.58	-	0.46	0.46	3.31	0.33	2.28	0.56	4.10	10.07
QL09-23-15	0.04	0.03	0.04	1.25	3.22	5.40	-	0.26	0.23	1.75	0.29	1.06	0.22	4.88	6.05
QL09-23-16	0.06	0.16	0.06	2.72	4.43	5.66	0.05	0.38	1.84	1.83	0.25	1.24	0.20	6.18	7.37
QL09-23-17	0.05	0.09	0.06	64.5	2.92	4.43	-	0.05	0.02	0.35	0.04	17.9	2.64	6.77	7.95
QL09-23-18	0.10	0.34	0.08	8.21	3.83	19.1	-	1.82	10.3	6.53	0.43	1.66	0.60	2.77	15.2

Table S1 Trace element compositions of muscovite, biotite and chlorite

	Tm	Yb	Lu	W	Tl	Pb	Bi	Th	U	Zr	Hf	Nb	Ta	Nb/Ta	Zr/Hf
	ppm														
QL09-23-19	0.22	1.05	0.26	4.26	3.41	56.9	-	9.23	38.1	20.6	1.23	3.25	0.41	7.99	16.7
QL09-24-1	-	-	-	53.3	3.76	3.10	-	-	-	0.27	0.05	79.6	14.0	5.67	5.74
QL09-24-4	0.01	0.23	0.08	74.9	3.86	3.03	-	0.01	0.01	0.94	0.13	128	21.9	5.81	7.06
QL09-24-5	-	0.15	0.06	71.2	3.53	2.94	-	-	-	1.03	0.07	120	20.7	5.79	14.8
QL09-24-6	0.01	0.24	0.09	103	3.75	3.59	-	-	-	1.07	0.11	108	15.7	6.89	9.8
QL09-24-7	0.02	0.14	0.11	126	3.84	4.24	-	-	0.01	2.03	0.29	205	44.7	4.60	6.99
QL09-24-8	0.01	0.27	0.10	144	3.81	3.39	-	-	0.01	1.57	0.21	199	43.8	4.55	7.36
QL09-24-9	0.01	0.28	0.11	126	4.21	3.88	-	-	-	2.04	0.25	186	38.6	4.82	8.03
QL09-24-10	0.03	0.33	0.10	115	4.01	3.62	-	-	-	1.60	0.24	143	16.4	8.71	6.76
QL09-24-11	-	0.07	0.03	58.5	3.82	3.18	-	-	-	0.75	0.13	93.9	17.2	5.45	5.58
QL09-25-1	-	-	0.01	33.1	2.56	3.93	-	-	0.02	0.43	0.05	28.5	2.93	9.72	8.34
QL09-25-4	-	-	0.02	45.3	2.20	4.06	-	0.19	-	0.42	0.08	30.1	4.00	7.53	5.33
QL09-25-7	-	-	0.02	68.9	2.99	7.91	-	-	-	0.91	0.23	161	21.9	7.36	3.94
QL09-26-5	-	-	0.01	30.4	2.74	4.76	-	-	-	0.44	0.12	54.5	7.03	7.75	3.75
QL09-26-6	0.03	0.20	0.10	48.9	2.55	7.77	-	0.61	0.08	0.70	0.11	25.3	3.14	8.05	6.37
QL09-26-7	-	-	0.03	53.6	2.46	4.50	-	0.07	0.03	0.61	0.09	30.9	3.99	7.75	6.81
QL09-27-10	-	-	-	61.2	2.50	3.38	-	0.03	-	0.10	0.01	51.4	8.27	6.22	6.97
QL09-27-11	-	-	-	61.0	2.14	7.24	-	0.09	-	0.14	-	42.7	5.26		
QL09-28-6	1.25	9.09	0.81	35.3	2.57	290	-	4.89	2.69	2.14	0.23	26.3	2.81	9.35	9.16
QL09-29-23	0.04	0.37	0.04	1.27	3.83	3.30	-	0.54	0.11	1.04	0.15	1.33	0.08	16.0	7.13
QL09-30-25	-	0.13	-	1.03	4.90	0.94	-	0.22	0.01	1.25	0.10	3.57	0.18	20.0	13.2

Table S2 Trace element compositions of zircon

	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Eu	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er	Tm	Yb	Lu	Li	SiO ₂	P	Ca	Ti	Y
	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	wt%	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm
QL09-27-1	0.0052	10.5	0.052	1.54	4.12	0.67	25.6	9.24	116	47.3	212	45.3	423	84.4		40.6	798		7.83	1312
QL09-27-10	0.0014	8.21	0.033	1.15	2.95	0.52	19.7	7.09	93.2	36.5	167	35.4	335	67.5	0.26	41.2	675		10.3	1060
QL09-27-11	0.022	14.8	0.061	1.39	3.07	0.46	15.8	5.53	65.8	25.2	107	21.9	202	39.0		41.3	358		12.5	727
QL09-27-12	6.16	53.7	2.87	13.8	7.55	0.81	39.8	17.0	235	98.2	473	106	1015	204	25.6	43.4	1686	200	5.00	2642
QL09-27-13	0.070	37.6	0.79	13.0	27.7	3.45	147	49.1	583	217	924	181	1562	292	23.4	41.0	1584		7.76	5548
QL09-27-14	3.78	27.3	1.63	8.67	11.7	0.31	74.5	35.6	500	206	963	204	1827	356	70.2	42.1	2350	126	5.09	5349
QL09-27-15	1.64	11.3	0.65	4.65	5.29	0.71	25.7	9.22	114	44.8	204	43.3	397	80.0	5.96	42.6	681	253	75.4	1283
QL09-27-16	0.44	9.50	0.21	1.98	3.45	0.76	25.5	9.12	121	48.8	226	48.9	461	94.8	0.49	41.9	739		24.2	1406
QL09-27-17	3.11	18.6	1.00	6.45	4.78	1.12	28.3	10.2	127	51.2	242	52.6	497	104	0.41	43.2	1074	867	22.0	1478
QL09-27-18		9.49	0.089	1.28	3.57	0.57	24.3	9.31	119	48.7	232	50.3	482	98.0		41.4	824		9.94	1423
QL09-27-19	5.85	25.9	2.66	13.9	14.2	0.68	65.0	31.2	449	181	900	204	1965	382	71.2	42.8	2278	533	11.2	4799
QL09-27-2	0.61	16.0	0.25	3.31	6.26	0.51	46.0	20.1	273	113	524	111	1011	197	3.05	42.0	1455		2.22	2968
QL09-27-20		7.84	0.088	1.72	3.97	0.76	27.3	10.4	131	51.7	243	52.2	497	102		41.3	937	26.2	12.3	1475
QL09-27-21	0.48	3.35	0.21	2.20	4.52	0.35	23.0	8.15	98.0	36.0	164	34.7	331	66.0	2.41	41.2	696		12.9	1075
QL09-27-22	0.034	9.19	0.079	1.76	4.30	0.96	27.8	10.5	134	54.7	258	55.5	526	109		41.1	876		13.8	1534
QL09-27-23	0.0041	7.29	0.099	1.68	3.72	0.70	23.0	8.40	104	40.4	182	37.8	348	70.4	5.27	42.2	640		10.2	1143
QL09-27-24	0.017	9.75	0.11	1.45	4.60	0.67	28.3	10.6	138	56.7	264	56.5	536	109		41.0	944		10.5	1555
QL09-27-3	0.039	10.3	0.096	1.69	4.94	0.62	32.3	11.8	150	59.1	265	54.7	502	98.5	3.34	41.3	788		6.31	1584
QL09-27-4	7.07	13.2	2.22	10.4	9.50	0.83	38.3	15.8	210	83.9	401	89.9	870	172	14.7	40.6	1348	87.0	9.43	2279
QL09-27-5	1.72	20.9	1.09	10.0	13.0	1.45	56.3	16.8	183	64.4	275	56.0	528	103	26.8	41.8	477	74.2	26.8	1727
QL09-27-6	3.93	28.8	2.33	11.5	12.6	0.87	56.7	26.6	368	151	731	164	1563	305	44.6	41.9	2074	427	5.79	4098

Table S2 Trace element compositions of zircon

	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Eu	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er	Tm	Yb	Lu	Li	SiO₂	P	Ca	Ti	Y
	ppm	wt%	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm														
QL09-27-7	0.79	16.3	0.28	2.16	5.59	0.28	38.8	17.3	247	103	484	103	933	181	7.63	40.9	1369	44.4	2.07	2703
QL09-27-8	0.0076	12.0	0.10	2.08	5.33	0.93	33.5	12.4	166	65.7	307	66.1	622	124		40.5	1027		10.9	1753
QL09-27-9	0.64	13.1	0.46	2.48	3.86	0.42	25.6	10.3	136	55.6	260	56.1	531	104	6.44	41.0	849	108	6.32	1548

Table S2 Trace element compositions of zircon

	ZrO₂	Nb	Hf	Ta	Pb	Pb	Pb	Pb	Th	U	Zr/Hf	Nb/Ta
	wt%	ppm										
QL09-27-1	66.1	2.05	11748	1.14	0.94	83.7	5.37	7.32	158	269	42	1.8
QL09-27-10	66.1	1.52	11256	0.90		63.8	3.95	4.77	105	201	44	1.7
QL09-27-11	66.1	2.11	11121	1.10	0.74	78.3	7.88	12.4	88.1	76.9	44	1.9
QL09-27-12	66.1	6.80	14137	3.94	2.62	314	23.0	17.0	288	984	35	1.7
QL09-27-13	66.1	5.87	11138	2.30	1.23	350	21.8	56.0	1154	1036	44	2.5
QL09-27-14	66.1	21.3	14902	12.5	11.7	732	57.7	44.4	849	2138	33	1.7
QL09-27-15	66.1	2.67	10950	0.95	13.9	67.5	14.2	16.3	108	171	45	2.8
QL09-27-16	66.1	2.44	10890	1.18	1.47	70.1	4.89	5.93	119	216	45	2.1
QL09-27-17	66.1	2.99	10264	1.24	0.91	78.7	5.44	7.17	139	244	48	2.4
QL09-27-18	66.1	2.71	10977	1.43	1.84	76.8	4.75	5.53	115	232	45	1.9
QL09-27-19	66.1	21.0	17102	13.8	29.0	707	71.0	48.1	742	2196	29	1.5
QL09-27-2	66.1	4.95	13564	3.83	3.39	325	22.2	21.7	499	976	36	1.3
QL09-27-20	66.1	1.91	10645	1.20	0.95	63.1	3.83	4.99	104	198	46	1.6
QL09-27-21	66.1	1.89	11898	0.96	0.83	163	12.1	7.81	170	415	41	2.0
QL09-27-22	66.1	2.79	10636	1.22	1.35	68.9	4.32	5.64	124	220	46	2.3
QL09-27-23	66.1	1.16	11131	0.68	0.49	46.5	2.84	4.70	96.1	140	44	1.7
QL09-27-24	66.1	2.87	11126	1.42	0.10	80.7	5.15	6.92	144	251	44	2.0
QL09-27-3	66.1	1.86	11990	1.08	1.16	88.3	5.92	9.41	198	292	41	1.7
QL09-27-4	66.1	7.25	12381	4.97	4.02	249	19.3	11.5	657	761	40	1.5
QL09-27-5	66.1	3.59	10289	1.04	3.71	245	21.1	34.8	517	470	48	3.4

Table S2 Trace element compositions of zircon

	ZrO₂	Nb	Hf	Ta	Pb	Pb	Pb	Pb	Th	U	Zr/Hf	Nb/Ta
	wt%	ppm										
QL09-27-6	66.1	16.9	14642	11.8	10.9	513	42.8	28.7	567	1591	33	1.4
QL09-27-7	66.1	8.53	13394	5.75	3.08	347	22.3	21.8	513	1032	37	1.5
QL09-27-8	66.1	3.09	11006	1.62	0.66	110	6.73	8.32	187	356	44	1.9
QL09-27-9	66.1	4.20	12111	2.80	7.85	181	19.8	19.6	213	505	40	1.5